

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Buarque, B., Câmara, S. F., Oukes, T., Júnior, E. P. L. (2025). Dynamics of entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil and the Netherlands: The role of universities to foster ecosystems and KIE firms in the Global South. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(3), 2025. e2024-0177. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250309>

How to cite this peer review report:

Buarque, B., Câmara, S. F., Oukes, T., Júnior, E. P. L. (2025). Peer review report for: Dynamics of entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil and the Netherlands: The role of universities to foster ecosystems and knowledge-intensive entrepreneurial firms in the Global South. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(3), 2025. e2024-0177. *Zenodo*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15558221>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Anas Mawadia , Université de Poitiers, Ecoles Universitaires de Management, Poitiers, France

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Anas Mawadia

Date review returned: 12-Jul-2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

Thank you very much for the opportunity to read your paper “DYNAMICS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS IN BRAZIL AND THE NETHERLANDS: THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES TO PROMOTE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT”. Overall, I appreciate the idea of multiple case study approach to compare the entrepreneurial ecosystems dynamics between two different regions in two different countries. The argumentation of the paper is clear even if it is too descriptive. In the following, I would like to point out where I perceive particular strengths of the paper as well as where might be room for improvement. I hope that you will find the comments I would like to share helpful in developing your paper further. Introduction: the introduction is long but incomplete. In fact, you need to justify clearly your gap and to which literature are you contributing entrepreneurship, ecosystems, dynamic capabilities, KIE, University and industry collaboration, innovation policy... we can perceive this difficulty of target literature and gap in your research question. You are proposing many research questions: Page 3 : “This paper studies how public policies affect the entrepreneurial ecosystem of a region” & Page 4 : “This study seeks to compare the influence of innovation policies at the entrepreneurial ecosystem and in the KIE firms, seeking to understand their influence on the development of dynamic capabilities, and on the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem”. You are proposing many objectives and many questions that is difficult to study in one paper. You need to propose one question and stick to it. One paper = one research question = one gap = one target literature. Trying to answer many questions make your paper fuzzy and it is especially the case with your results and contributions, we will see that later.

Literature review: this section is well written and gives essential references. Authors need to justify the choice of certain literature. Why are you mobilizing KIE literature, dynamic capabilities and innovation policies ? What is the interest of using them? How they contributes to clarify the studied research question? Fortunately, the figure 1 shed some light on the link between these theories but does not explain their interest and clarifications.

Methodology: this part needs many ameliorations. First you need to justify your methodology, the choice of qualitative one, the method chosen (you did not name, but it seems that you are following a multiple case studies). Please add methodological references. Authors need to pay attention to the fact that Table 1 is not really an interview script as we don't know exactly the questions posed by the authors to interviewees. Table 1 is more a table for thematic analysis (themes and authors). Table 2: we need to know the profile of each interviewee and the region. Authors need to give more information on the coding strategy and the codes used to analyze the qualitative data.

Results: They are interesting and give many field information. However we notice that no interview verbatim is used, why?. The results are too descriptive and tries to respond to many research objectives. Your comparison of both regions arrive late in the results section. I suggest that you start with that and then explain each dimension, especially those where differences are identified. Authors need also to illustrate the model proposed in figure 1 by clear field examples from both regions.

Discussion: no discussion section is proposed. Authors need to discuss the literature mobilized through their results.

Conclusion: Authors don't specify clearly their theoretical and managerial contributions. Limitations are briefly discussed and plausible avenues for further research are suggested based on the findings. In sum, I believe that the paper can provides novel insights on entrepreneurial ecosystems by comparing these two regions if some ameliorations are done. I hope that these remarks will help you. Thanks again for the opportunity to read your paper and good luck!

Reviewer 2 Report

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Author's Response

DYNAMICS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS IN BRAZIL AND THE NETHERLANDS: THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES TO PROMOTE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Dear Editors and Reviewers,

We appreciate all the suggestions and comments made to our paper. We agree with the reviewers' comments and understand that the paper's text does indeed have a lot of potential, but it needed several improvements. We sought to make the improvements indicated by the reviewers, substantially modifying all sections of the paper. One challenge in including this new information was the recommendation not to exceed the maximum of 8,800 words – we were unable to reach this number, as it was necessary to include a lot of new text to attend the Reviewers' request.

We ask that if it is necessary to reduce the number of words, we can do so in a final version of the paper. The same applies to the revised version of the text in English – we will request a complete review by a professional, once we have the final version approved by the journal.

We are including a file with the responses for the Reviewers, pointing out all the improvements included in the paper. In the article file, the new text is highlighted in yellow. We also changed the title of the paper, to be more in line with the topics covered and also with the Special Issue.

Furthermore, we are at your disposal to make any other adjustments that may be necessary to the text of the paper.

Thank you again,

Authors of the paper.

Dear Editors and Reviewers,

We appreciate all the suggestions and comments made to our paper. We agree with the reviewers' comments and understand that the paper's text does indeed have a lot of potential, but it needed several improvements. We sought to make the improvements indicated by the reviewers, substantially modifying all sections of the paper. One challenge in including this new information was the recommendation not to exceed the maximum of 8,800 words – we were unable to reach this number, as it was necessary to include a lot of new text to attend the Reviewers' request.

We ask that if it is necessary to reduce the number of words, we can do so in a final version of the paper. The same applies to the revised version of the text in English – we will request a complete review by a professional, once we have the final version approved by the journal.

Below are included responses to reviewers, pointing out all the improvements included in the paper. In the article file, the new text is highlighted in yellow. We also changed the title of the paper, to be more in line with the topics covered.

Furthermore, we are at your disposal to make any other adjustments that may be necessary to the text of the paper. Thank you again,

Authors of the paper.

INTRODUCTION

Reviewer 1

the introduction is long but incomplete. In fact, you need to justify clearly your gap and to which literature are you contributing entrepreneurship, ecosystems, dynamic capabilities, KIE, University and industry collaboration, innovation policy... we can perceive this difficulty of target literature and gap in your research question. You are proposing many research questions: Page 3 : "This paper studies how public policies affect the entrepreneurial ecosystem of a region" & Page 4 : "This study seeks to compare the influence of innovation policies at the entrepreneurial ecosystem and in the KIE firms, seeking to understand their influence on the development of dynamic capabilities, and on the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem". You are proposing many objectives and many questions that is difficult to study in one paper. You need to propose one question and stick to it. One paper = one research question = one gap = one target literature. Trying to answer many questions make your paper fuzzy and it is especially the case with your results and contributions, we will see that later.

Reviewer 2

- I recommend that the Introduction be much shorter and objective. The gap in the literature comes too late, as well as the research question*
- I believe the research question is too generic/broad: "This paper studies how public policies affect the entrepreneurial ecosystem of a region, and how these policies influence the development of dynamic capabilities in KIE firms." o Is it possible to focus further on the role of universities, which is the central theme of this special issue?*

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reviewer 1

this section is well written and gives essential references. Authors need to justify the choice of certain literature. Why are you mobilizing KIE literature, dynamic capabilities and innovation policies ? What is the interest of using them? How they contributes to clarify the studied research question? Fortunately, the figure 1 shed some light on the link between these theories but does not explain their interest and clarifications.

Reviewer 2

- There are a number of concepts and ideas underspecified and undertheorized. For instance: "The universities also play a significant role in the operationalization of dynamic capabilities within the context of public policies for entrepreneurship. Their relevance extends through their ability to act as centers of knowledge and innovation, providing fundamental resources for these dynamic capabilities"*
- What are dynamic capabilities?*
- Why do universities play a significant role in generating dynamic capabilities?*
- Same for "absorptive capacity": define better; improve the theory*

METHODOLOGY

Reviewer 1

this part needs many ameliorations. First you need to justify your methodology, the choice of qualitative one, the method chosen (you did not name, but it seems that you are following a multiple case studies). Please add methodological references. Authors need to pay attention to the fact that Table 1 is not really an interview script as we don't know exactly the questions posed by the authors to interviewees. Table 1 is more a table for thematic analysis (themes and authors). Table 2: we need to know the profile of each interviewee and the region. Authors need to give more information on the coding strategy and the codes used to analyze the qualitative data.

Reviewer 2

- *It is not clear for me the criteria for contrasting the cases of Ceará and Twente. Please see Eisenhardt's papers on case selection and comparison:*
 - *Eisenhardt, K. M., & Graebner, M. E. (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. Academy of management journal, 50(1), 25-32.*
 - *Eisenhardt, K. M. (1991). Better stories and better constructs: The case for rigor and comparative logic. Academy of Management review, 16(3), 620-627.*
 - *Eisenhardt, K. M. (2021). What is the Eisenhardt Method, really?. Strategic organization, 19(1), 147-160.*
- *How was ChatGPT used? Please provide more details, including prompts if appropriate*

RESULTS

Reviewer 1

They are interesting and give many field information. However we notice that no interview verbatim is used, why?. The results are too descriptive and tries to respond to many research objectives. Your comparison of both regions arrive late in the results section. I suggest that you start with that and then explain each dimension, especially those where differences are identified. Authors need also to illustrate the model proposed in figure 1 by clear field examples from both regions.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Anas Mawadia

Date review returned: 31-Jan-2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

Thanks to the authors for this new version, which incorporates a large number of the suggested improvements. You have improved the coherence of the conceptual framework by focusing on the model that you suggested in figure one and the main axes of entrepreneurship policies, KIE firms and dynamic capabilities. My main remarks are regarding the discussion and theoretical contributions.

In fact, some point of improvement are still to be done at this stage. The main one is to really precise what are your theoretical contributions to literature : you precise in page 25 : “The study contributes to the literature by presenting the similarities and differences in the implementation of entrepreneurship and innovation policies between two regions with different levels of development. » But this is the analysis that you did and not your theoretical contributions. You state that : « The results provide insights for the discussion on entrepreneurship and innovation policies, and on the role of universities in implementing these policies. The study also presents how universities can play a relevant role in the development of knowledge-intensive companies. In addition to contributing to the literature, the findings of the paper are also relevant for the formulation of public policies and for university administrators and researchers working with Knowledge-Intensive Entrepreneurship ? ». So what are precisely these contributions and the link with existing literature. In some how you need to precise how did you fill the gap, and don't be descriptive. Your discussion section should precise what we learn as new or interesting regarding the main axes of entrepreneurship policies, KIE firms and dynamic capabilities, and your contribution to the model shown in figure 1. Don't say it, prove it. Your results show some interesting entrepreneurial policies and dynamic capabilities based on the comparison of both regions, but you need to make the necessary discussion to show how you fill the gap. I wish you good luck and I am convinced that these changes are not very complicated to make.

Reviewer 2 Report

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.